

Dissociation Constants of 2, 2'-Dimercapto Diethyl Ether in Different Media

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The dissociation constants of 2, 2'-dimercapto diethyl ether have been determined by potentiometric and polarographic techniques at ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$ (NaClO_4) in several aquo-organic media such as ethanol, methanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol and acetonitrile. The values of pK_1 and pK_2 were found to have linear relationship with inverse dielectric constant of the media. The effects of ionic strength, ethanol concentration and temperature on the dissociation constants have also been studied. From the variation of pK_1 and pK_2 with temperature, the values of ΔH , ΔS and ΔG at 30° are calculated.

2, 2'-DIMERCAPTO diethyl ether belongs to an important class of mercapto compounds which have wide applications in biological, pharmaceutical and industrial fields. Its polarographic behaviour has already been reported by the authors¹ but no reference regarding its dissociation constants could be traced in the literature. Two -SH groups in 2,2'-dimercapto diethyl ether have their corresponding dissociation constants whose knowledge is essential for understanding the chemistry of this compound for two main reasons; first, many reactions of thiols occur through the mercaptide ions and second, the dissociation constants provide important information about the distribution of electrons in mercaptans. Their values reveal the proportions of different ionic species at any *pH* and this information is useful in ultraviolet spectrophotometry and preparative chemistry. Moreover, these values are involved in the study of complexation reactions of such compounds with metals. Hence it has been considered worthwhile to determine the dissociation constants of 2,2'-dimercaptodiethyl ether in several aquo-organic media such as ethanol, methanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol and acetonitrile. The effects of varying ionic strength, ethanol concentration and temperature on the dissociation constants have also been studied. The values of ΔH , ΔS and ΔG determined at 30° are also reported.

Experimental

2,2'-dimercapto diethyl ether, $\text{O}(\text{CH}_2\text{CH}_2\text{-SH})_2$, (referred herein as $\text{R}(\text{SH})_2$) was supplied by Evan's Chemetics, Inc., N.Y. and all other chemicals were of Anal-R(BDH) grade. Freshly prepared solutions were always used to avoid the effects of ageing and air-oxidation. The media used in the study consists of 40% (by volume) ethanol, methanol, *n*-propanol, isopropanol and acetonitrile. The entire study was carried out at ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$, maintained

by NaClO_4 and at temperature $20^\circ \pm 0.1^\circ$ except where specific conditions are mentioned.

A manual polarograph with scalamp galvanometer was employed for polarographic measurements using S.C.E. as reference electrode. The capillary used had the following characteristics: $m = 2.652 \text{ mg/sec}$, $t = 2.65 \text{ sec}$ and $m^{2/3}t^{1/6} = 2.253 \text{ mg}^{2/3}\text{sec}^{-1/2}$. The solutions were prepared in 25 ml volumetric flask by the addition of a known volume of the standard solutions so as to give the required concentrations of the various contents and transferred to the thermostated H-Cell. The solution was flushed with pure nitrogen for 25-30 min. before each polarogram was recorded and an inert atmosphere was maintained above the solution during electrolysis. NaClO_4 was used as supporting electrolyte and *pH* of the solution was maintained by Clark and Lub's buffer. Half-wave potentials of the waves were determined from the conventional log plots and the value of overall dissociation constant of sulphhydryl group was obtained from the plots between $E_{1/2}$ and *pH*.

A Cambridge Bench *pH* meter was used for *pH* measurements. A solution (25 ml) containing 4.0 mM $(\text{RSH})_2$ and requisite amount of NaClO_4 to maintain the ionic strength $\mu = 0.1 M$, was titrated with CO_2 -free, 0.1M NaOH. The two dissociation constants for -SH groups were calculated from the titration curve applying the method of Albert and Serjeant.²

Results and Discussion

2,2'-dimercaptodiethyl ether containing two-SH groups has two replaceable hydrogen ions (I, II)

Equations (1) and (2) illustrate the kinds of equilibria for which the dissociation constants K_1 and K_2 are determined.

It has been shown earlier¹ that 2,2'-dimercapto diethyl ether produces anodic wave associated with an adsorption prewave in all the media used in the present study. The polarograms of 0.5 mM R(SH)₂ in 40% non-aqueous media were drawn at different pH values using Clark and Lub's buffer solutions. $E_{1/2}$ of the main wave as well as of the prewave were found to shift towards more negative potential with increase in pH indicating the liberation of H⁺ ions at the electrode surface. The values of pK₂ in different media were obtained from the plots of $E_{1/2}$ versus pH where the point of intersection of two linear portions corresponded to the overall dissociation constant of sulphhydryl group³.

Values of pK₁ and pK₂ in different media: The values of dissociation constants (pK₁ and pK₂) in several aquo-organic media (Table 1) are found to follow the order

TABLE 1—VALUES OF pK₁ AND pK₂ IN DIFFERENT MEDIA

Media (40%)	Potentiometric method		Polarographic method
	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₂
Acetonitrile	9.32	9.98	10.04
Methanol	9.35	10.07	10.18
Ethanol	9.40	10.20	10.21
n-propanol	9.45	10.33	10.35
iso-propanol	9.48	10.38	10.50

which is in reverse order of their dielectric constant (D) values.⁴ The plots of pK₁ and pK₂ against 1/D were found to be linear in agreement with Born's relation.⁵

The values of pK₂ obtained polarographically are in close agreement with those calculated by potentiometry. The study of the following effects on dissociation constants of R(SH)₂ was made by potentiometric method since it determines the values of pK₁ and pK₂ both whereas the polarographic technique yields the value of pK₂ only.

Effects of ethanol concentration, ionic strength and temperature: The values of pK₁ and pK₂ are found to increase with increasing ethanol concentration (Table 2) showing linear relationship with 1/D (Fig. 1). The values of dielectric constant for

Fig. 1. Plots of pK₁ and pK₂ against 1/D at various ethanol concentrations. Curves—(1) for pK₁ and (2) for pK₂.

different ethanol-water mixtures were taken from the literature⁴. It may be seen from Table 3 that the values of dissociation constant decrease with increase in ionic strength of the solution and this observation is in agreement with the Debye-Hückel equation in the form.⁶

$$pK = pK_0 - [A\sqrt{\mu}/1 + \alpha\sqrt{\mu}] + C\mu \quad \dots (3)$$

TABLE 2—VALUES OF pK_1 AND pK_2 IN VARIOUS ETHANOL CONCENTRATION

Ethanol concentration (% by volume)	Dielectric constant (D)	1/D	pK_1	pK_2
10	74.60	1.341×10^{-2}	9.28	10.03
20	68.66	1.456 "	9.32	10.06
30	62.63	1.597 "	9.35	10.13
40	56.50	1.770 "	9.40	10.20
50	50.38	1.985 "	9.47	10.26
60	44.67	2.240 "	9.52	10.37
70	39.14	2.555 "	9.57	10.48
80	33.90	2.950 "	9.70	10.64

TABLE 3—VALUES OF pK_1 AND pK_2 AT VARIOUS IONIC STRENGTH AND TEMPERATURES IN 40% ETHANOLIC MEDIA

Ionic strength (μ)	20°C			30°C			40°C					
	0.025	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.80	0.025	0.05	0.10	0.20	0.40	0.80
pK_1	9.48	9.44	9.40	9.09	8.97	8.73						
pK_2	10.61	10.54	10.20	9.94	9.82	9.54						
Temp.	20°C			30°C			40°C					
pK_1	9.40			9.33			9.28					
pK_2	10.20			10.10			10.03					

These values decreased with increase in temperature also and the plots of pK_1 and pK_2 against $1/T$ were found to be linear (Fig. 2) agreeing with the relationship proposed by Pitzer⁷. From the variation of

pK_1 and pK_2 with temperature, values of ΔH , ΔS and ΔG have been determined at 30° for both the equilibria steps (equations 1 and 2) by applying the

Fig. 2. Plots of pK_1 and pK_2 against $1/T$.
Curves—(1) for pK_1 and (2) for pK_2 .

usual thermodynamic relations⁸ and found to be 2.49 KCal/mole, -34.33 cal/mole/deg. and 12.89 K. cal/mole for eqn. (1) and 3.47 K.cal/mole, -34.59 cal/mole/deg. and 13.95 Kcal/mole for eqn. (2) respectively.

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